

Low-Temperature Luminescence Spectroscopy of Violet Sr-Al-O:Eu²⁺ Phosphor Particles

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Abstract : Violet Sr-Al-O:Eu²⁺ phosphor particles were synthesized from a metal-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) solution of Sr, Al, Eu, and particulate alumina via spray drying and sintering in a reducing atmosphere. The crystal structures and emission properties at 85-300 K were investigated. The composition of the violet Sr-Al-O:Eu²⁺ phosphor particles was determined from various Sr-Al-O:Eu²⁺ phosphors by their emission properties' dependence on temperature. The highly crystalline SrAl₁₂O₁₉:Eu²⁺ emission phases were confirmed by their crystallite sizes and the activation energies for the 4f_{5d}-8S_{7/2} transition of the Eu²⁺ ion. These results showed that the material identification for the violet Sr-Al-O:Eu²⁺ phosphor was accomplished by the low-temperature luminescence measurements.

Keywords : low temperature luminescence spectroscopy, material identification, strontium aluminates phosphor, emission properties

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